

№3
27.06.2023

RESEARCH AND IMPLEMENTATION
TADQIQ VA TATBIQ
ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALI

CERTIFICATE
№ 078777

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

- ✓ ANIQ FANLAR
- ✓ TABIIY FANLAR
- ✓ SIYOSIY FANLAR
- ✓ IJTIMOIIY FANLAR

- ✓ IQTISOD FANLARI
- ✓ TEXNIKA FANLARI
- ✓ TIBBIYOT FANLARI
- ✓ PEDAGOGIKA FANLARI

fer-teach.uz

@fer-teach_uz

Bosh muharrir:

F.M.Muxtarov
t.f.b. PhD

Jurnal oyda bir
marta nashr etiladi.

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, rus, ingliz va
qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy
kommunikatsiya agentligida
2023-yil 3-mayda
№078777
raqam bilan ro'yxatga
olingan

Murojaat uchun

@ferteach_uz

+99893-343-13-14

<https://fer-teach.uz>

Mas'ul muharrir

S.I.Zokirov - f.-m.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

Taxrir hay'ati:

T.M.Abdullayev – t.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

N.I.Ibrokhimov – f.-m.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

A.R.Nurmatov – tarix f.b. PhD., NamDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

D.F.To'xtasinov - ped.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

J.T.Moldaliyev - bio. f. n., dotsent. OshDU, Osh, Qirg'iziston

T.M.Bakirov - ped. f.b. PhD, FarDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

B.B.Mallabayev - tarix f.n., dotsent. NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

X.K.Boymirzayev - ped. f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

I.U.Kuzikulov - tarix f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

B.T.Mirzadjanov - tarix f.b. PhD, , NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

M.A.Maxmudov - tarix f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

B.Ya.Tursunov - tarix f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

S.B.Atajonova - ped.f.b.PhD, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston

APPLICATION OF THE CORRELATION THEORY IN THE EXAMPLE OF THE ALIGNMENT OF EXPERIMENTAL DATA

S. Kukieva

Senior lecturer at Ferghana State University

Annotation: In the article, using the method of least squares for example, results are obtained closer to the exact value of unknown parameters.

Keywords: least squares method, functional dependence, statistical dependence, correlation dependence, correlation table, sample correlation coefficient

ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ТЕОРИИ КОРРЕЛЯЦИИ НА ПРИМЕРЕ ВЫРАВНИВАНИЯ ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ДАННЫХ

С. Кукиева

*старший преподаватель Ферганского государственного
университета*

Аннотация: В статье на примере метода наименьших квадратов получены результаты, более близкие к точному значению неизвестных параметров.

Ключевые слова: метод наименьших квадратов, функциональная зависимость, статистическая зависимость, корреляционная зависимость, корреляционная таблица, выборочный коэффициент корреляции.

It is known that the processes occurring in plants and in living organisms are caused by the influence of a large number of interrelated factors, among which there are the main ones that determine the main properties and characteristics of a process or phenomenon, and secondary ones.

How to find in the form of a formula the relationship between two random variables obtained in the results of observations? How much does a change in one quantity affect a change in another ?

The least squares method has a strict mathematical justification, therefore, the results of calculations obtained with its help are considered to be closer to the exact value of unknown parameters a and b .

The variables X and Y can be related to:

- a) functional dependence;
- b) statistical dependence, in the particular case of correlation.

The dependence is called correlation if each possible value of one quantity is compared with a numerical characteristic corresponding to the distribution of the other.

A table with two inputs, in which the results of observations are recorded in ascending order indicating the frequency of pairs of features, is called correlation.

According to the correlation table, it is possible to construct empirical regression lines X on Y and Y on X . The leveling "smooth" curve is called the theoretical regression line. The simplest is linear. The strength or tightness of the linear correlation dependence is determined by the sample correlation coefficient:

$$r = \frac{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{X}_B)(y_i - \bar{Y}_B)}{\sigma_B(X) \cdot \sigma_B(\bar{Y})}, \quad r \in (-1;1)$$

If $|r|=1$, then the studied relationship between the quantities is linearly dependent. If $r=0$, then there is no linear correlation between X and Y , i.e. signs of independence.

Example. The dependence of the ear length X (in cm) on the number of grains in the ear Y (pieces) is characterized by the following table:

x_i , length,cm	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
y_i , the number of grains in an ear	16,0	20,3	23,5	24,5	28,0	29,0	29,5	31,0

- show that the correlation is linear;
- using the least squares method to find the linear relationship between X and Y ;
- find a sample correlation coefficient.

Solution: Construct points $M(x_i, y_i)$ in the xOy coordinate system

The figure shows that the points are located along a straight line. To determine the coefficients a and b , we will make an auxiliary table.

№	x_i , length,	y_i , the number of grains	x_i^2	$x_i \cdot y_i$
1	7	16	49	112
2	8	20,3	64	162,4
3	9	23,5	81	211,5
4	10	24,5	100	245
5	11	28,0	121	308
6	12	29,0	144	348
7	13	29,5	169	383,5
8	14	31,0	196	434
	$\sum x_i = 84$	$\sum y_i = 201,8$	$\sum x_i^2 = 924$	$\sum x_i y_i = 2204,4$

The system of equations has the form:

$$\begin{cases} 924a + 84b = 2204,4 \\ 84a + 8b = 201,8 \end{cases}$$

from where we find: $a = 2,03$, $b = 3,85$ and $y = 2,03x + 3,85$

Let's now determine the sample correlation coefficient. We find the average value of the samples:

$$\bar{X}_B = \frac{84}{8} = 10,5$$

$$\bar{Y}_B = \frac{201,8}{8} = 25,2$$

Let's make an auxiliary table.

№	x_i	y_i	$x_i - \bar{X}_B$	$y_i - \bar{Y}_B$	$(x_i - \bar{X}_B) \cdot (y_i - \bar{Y}_B)$	$(x_i - \bar{X}_B)^2$	$(y_i - \bar{Y}_B)^2$
1	7	16	-3,5	-9,2	32,2	12,25	84,64
2	8	20,3	-2,5	-4,9	12,25	6,25	24,01
3	9	23,5	-1,5	-1,7	2,55	2,25	2,89
4	10	24,5	-0,5	-0,7	0,35	0,25	0,49
5	11	28	0,5	2,8	1,4	0,25	7,84
6	12	29	1,5	3,8	5,7	2,25	14,44
7	13	29,5	2,5	4,3	10,75	6,25	18,49
8	14	31	3,5	5,8	20,3	12,25	33,64
9							
					$\sum = 85,5$	$\sum = 42$	$\sum = 186,44$

We have

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{X}_B) \cdot (y_i - \bar{Y}_B)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{X}_B)^2 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{Y}_B)}} = \frac{85,5}{\sqrt{42 \cdot 186,44}} = \frac{85,5}{88,49} = 0,97$$

The correlation coefficient is close to one, but the relationship between the values of X and Y is linearly dependent.

Literature

- 1.L. Bolshev N., Smirnov N.V. Tables of mathematical statistics, 1983, 416 p.
2. J. Barra.R. Basic concepts of mathematical statistics. M., 1974, 58 p.
3. Kukiyeva S. Research in the field of Hilbert theory concerning the three statements of mathematics. International scientific journal Electron Create Your Future With Us "All sciences". No. 5 , 2022, pp. 68-75
4. Kukiyeva S. , O.Raxmatova. Sufficient conditions for uniform convergence of random series. International Journal on integrated education. Volume 3, Issue I, Jan 2020 |34
5. Kukiyeva S. Research in the field of Hilbert theory concerning the three statements of mathematics. International scientific journal Electron Create Your Future With Us "All sciences". No. 5 , 2022, pp. 68-75
6. Kukiyeva S. Application of testing the hypothesis of exponential expansion of a general population in a single problem. Ilmiy conference. NamDU, UR FA V.I. Romanovsky nomidagi Mathematics Institute. "Esh matematiklarning yangi theoremalari - 2018". October 18-19, 2018. 25-26 b.
7. To'xtasinov , D. F., & Abdupattoyeva , D. A. qizi. (2023). BOSHLANG'ICH SINF O'QUVCHILARINING GEOMETRIK TASAVVURINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA FOYDALANILADIGAN METODLAR. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(4), 771–773. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/2227>
8. To'xtasinov , D. F., Gafurova , M. A., & Abdullayeva, S. H. qizi. (2023). BOSHLANG'ICH SINFDA IJODIY TAFAKKURNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK ASOSLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(4), 729–733. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/2220>